

Investigating Phonetic Changes in the English Language

Zebo Botirova Xakimjon qizi

Namangan davlat universiteti,

Ingliz tili va adabiyoti kafedrası, dotsenti, PhD

E-mail: ziziko_90@mail.ru

Abduvaliyeva Durdona Anvarjon qizi

Namangan Davlat Universiteti,

Filologiya va tillarni o'qitish: ingliz tili yo'nalishi,

4-kurs talabasi,

E-mail: abduvaliyevadurdona105@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola vaqt o'tishi bilan fonetik o'zgarishlarni to'rganish orqali ingliz tilining dinamik tabiatini o'rganadi. Ingliz fonetikasining eski ingliz tilidan zamonaviy ingliz tiliga evolyutsiyasini kuzatish orqali ushbu tadqiqot talaffuzdagi sezilarli o'zgarishlarni aniqlaydi va bu o'zgarishlarga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni o'rganadi. Tarixiy tilshunoslik va fonologik nazariyalarni tahlil qilish orqali ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilidagi davom etayotgan fonetik o'zgarishlar jarayonini yoritib beradi, uning til o'zlashtirish, dialektal o'zgarishlar va sotsiolingvistik hodisalarga ta'sirini yoritadi

Kalit so'zlar: *Fonologik o'zgarish, fonema, refonemitizatsiya, unli tovushning katta o'zgarishi, ot kelishigi, sifatdosh kelishigi, fe'l kelishigi.*

Аннотация: В этой статье исследуется динамическая природа английского языка путем изучения фонетических изменений с течением времени. Прослеживая эволюцию английской фонетики от древнеанглийского до современного английского, это исследование выявляет существенные

изменения в произношении и изучает факторы, влияющие на эти изменения. Анализируя историческую лингвистику и фонологические теории, это исследование проливает свет на продолжающийся процесс фонетических изменений в английском языке, его влияние на овладение языком, диалектные изменения и социолингвистические явления.

Ключевые слова: *фонологическое изменение, фонема, рефонемизация, большая смена гласных, склонение существительного, склонение прилагательного, спряжение глаголов.*

Annotation. This article explores the dynamic nature of the English language by examining phonetic changes over time. By tracing the evolution of English phonetics from Old English to Modern English, this study identifies significant shifts in pronunciation and investigates the factors influencing these changes. Through an analysis of historical linguistics and phonological theories, this research sheds light on the ongoing process of phonetic change in English, highlighting its implications for language acquisition, dialectal variation, and sociolinguistic phenomena.

Key words: *Phonological change, phoneme, rephonemization, great vowel change, noun declension, adjective declension, verb conjugations.*

Introduction.

The English language, like all living languages, is constantly evolving. One of the most fascinating aspects of this evolution is the change in pronunciation, known as phonetic change. Phonetic changes have occurred throughout the history of English, shaping the way words are spoken and understood. From the transition from Old English to Middle English, and from Middle English to Modern English, the language has undergone significant phonetic transformations. This article explores the phenomenon of phonetic changes in the English language, tracing its historical development, identifying key patterns, and examining the factors that drive these changes. By delving into the rich history of English phonetics, we can gain a deeper

understanding of the dynamic nature of language evolution and its implications for contemporary English speakers.

Main body

Phonological change is any sound change that alters the distribution of phonemes in a language. In other words, a language develops a new system of oppositions among its phonemes. Old contrasts may disappear, new ones may emerge, or they may simply be rearranged. One process of phonological change is rephonemicization, in which the distribution of phonemes changes by either addition of new phonemes or a reorganization of existing phonemes. Phonetic change can occur without any modification to the phoneme inventory or phonemic correspondences. This change is purely allophonic or subphonemic. This can entail one of two changes: either the phoneme turns into a new allophone—meaning the phonetic form changes—or the distribution of allophones of the phoneme changes.

Great Vowel change in English language. With the development of English linguistics in the Renaissance and the expansion of English application environment, middle English linguistics gradually developed into modern English linguistics. One of the English linguistics vowel change is most obvious, vowel pronunciation tongue raised, and is also reduced a lot, especially after the vowel and unit has had the obvious change, only the double vowel pronunciation method is relatively stable. For example, the vowel of a vowel [a] is moved forward and gradually improved; When the vowel [e] is pronounced, the tongue moves forward, and the opening degree becomes smaller and more similar to [I]. [I] the pronunciation is mainly supplemented by the corresponding phoneme, similar to [ai], [ei]. The [ou] pronunciation of diphthongs also changes to [au]. The loss of inflections in English refers to the reduction in the number and complexity of grammatical endings that indicated the grammatical function of a word. Old English had a rich system of inflections, inherited from its Germanic roots. However, over time, many of these

inflections were lost, leading to changes in pronunciation and grammar.

Noun Declensions: Old English nouns had different forms depending on their grammatical case. In Modern English, these inflections have mostly disappeared, and word order and prepositions are used to indicate grammatical relationships.

Verb Conjugations: Old English verbs also had different forms depending on tense, mood, and person. For example, the verb "lufian" (to love) had different forms such as "lufie" (present indicative), "lufode" (past indicative), "lufode" (past subjunctive), and "lufian" (infinitive). In Modern English, many of these inflections have disappeared, and auxiliary verbs (e.g., "do," "will," "have") are used to indicate tense and mood.

Adjective Declensions: Old English adjectives had different forms depending on the gender, case, and number of the noun they modified. For example, the adjective "eald" (old) had different forms such as "eald" (masculine nominative singular), "ealde" (masculine genitive singular), "ealdan" (masculine dative singular), "ealde" (feminine nominative singular), "ealdre" (feminine genitive singular), "ealdre" (feminine dative singular), etc. In Modern English, most adjectives have the same form regardless of gender, case, or number.

The loss of inflections in English has led to a more analytic grammar, where word order, prepositions, and auxiliary verbs are used to convey grammatical relationships rather than inflectional endings.

Conclusion. This study has provided insights into the intricate process of phonetic changes in the English language. By tracing the historical development of English phonetics and exploring the factors driving these changes, we have gained a deeper understanding of the dynamic nature of language evolution. Through continued research and analysis, we can further elucidate the mechanisms behind phonetic changes, thereby enhancing our comprehension of the rich and ever-evolving tapestry of the English language.

References:

1. Henrich Hock, Hans (1991). Principles of Historical Linguistics (Second ed.). Berlin; New York: Walter de Gruyter. pp. 53–4.
2. Crowley, Terry; Bower, Claire (2010). An Introduction to Historical Linguistics (4th ed.). Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press. p. 69. ISBN 9780195365542.
3. Baugh, Albert C. and Thomas Cable. *A History of the English Language.* Routledge, 2018.
4. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/article/25895422.pdf>.
5. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Phonological_history_of_English.